

HUMAN MENTAL BLINDNESS

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At the beginning of a decade where the human race has seen both a potent virus pandemic and one of the worst USA presidential election scenarios in history, many questions have arisen as to how can educated and supposedly intelligent human beings have allowed the various acts of disruption and devastation to occur, which we have all witnessed. And this, especially in a world which might claim to be much more advanced than previous centuries; where education for most is freely available to give them the faculties of true facts, clear perception and analysis of all situations.

So as to grasp some of the concepts in this paper, readers may need to have attempted to understand the paper "Artificial Intelligence v Human Consciousness"; (AI v HC) as matters related to the clarification of what human consciousness is, are laid out in that paper. Read at least the sections on Reincarnation and Human Intellect.

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Human Mental Blindness

Introduction

The whole world continues to see that millions of educated people are unable to clearly perceive the truth about global and important issues. Such clearly obvious matters as the authenticated outcome of the USA presidential election or the scientifically proved efficacy of the vaccination protection for a potent virus infection. Many people are completely unable to comprehend how these intelligent and educated people cannot themselves see the truth which stares them in the face, and is in many ways indisputable.

In this paper I will introduce and examine the phenomenon of human mental blindness. This will attempt to clarify the true reasons behind such blindness and thereby clarify for all of us how it is that truth cannot be comprehended when the evidence for it is there for all to examine for themselves; to clear up their doubts or to redirect their stance.

How Can Truth be Hidden?

There is an ancient analogy of how human beings become unable to perceive the facts of a situation which are plainly before their sense perceptions. It is called the "*snake in the rope scenario*". In the early morning a person is sitting in a room where there is a coil of rope in the corner. As the light of dawn begins to show the rope, the person imagines it is a large snake. Along with this false perception comes the fear of the snake with the many solutions about what to do about the situation. This analogy has served to clarify how the human mind is unable to perceive the reality of a situation presented to it.

Many questions have been examined about this simple situation, which is used to demonstrate human mental ignorance. The truth of the situation has been masked by an imaginary image formed in the mind of the observer. All the while this image is believed to be the true situation, the person cannot be freed from the fear of being attacked by a snake. There have been three basic routes proposed to lead the person out of this false perception. The first is that the observer can realise that the rope is not a snake by remembering that previously it was seen to be a rope. Secondly, another person who knows it is not a snake, arrived at by personal previous observation, can inform the misguided person. Thirdly, in time when the light of dawn increases sufficiently the person will see clearly that it is a rope. All three are the gaining of true knowledge over falsehood.

This false perception has been described as concealing the knowledge of truth with either absence of knowledge, false knowledge or doubt. Ignorance has these three causes.

We must be clear; there never was a real snake in the rope; but that the internal image of a non-existent snake, created within the mind of the individual, has caused real human reactions; fear and other emotions requiring perhaps more real actions by that person.

The causes of real actions are in reality illusory. They are all a product arising from the state of the human mind. They have no real substance. If they were substantial then they could not be easily removed. For example, the total darkness in a closed room vanishes when a door is opened where there is light outside. The light enters the room and the darkness is gone. The darkness does not pour out of the open door of the room and take away the light. This makes it clear that darkness, as much as it may create problems, actually has no substance. If darkness had substance it could not be so easily removed. The light has real substance; the darkness does not. This is my meaning of the word illusory here. That which is unreal in the physical world creates real reactions.

It is a fundamental principle that truth remains unaffected by time, as light is unaffected by darkness; but also falsehood cannot stand the test of time; just as darkness cannot survive the onslaught of the light. This should be clear to all of us.

We can turn this around and say that where recorded knowledge arising within human consciousness has survived many thousands of years, we can have some assurance that it is the truth. History shows that many belief systems have passed into obscurity or have mutated to be unrecognisable as their original scriptures state. They were less true.

It is in this respect we should give great respect to the Upanishads of the Vedanta system of thought. These were writings put down thousands of years ago; but prior to that time they were passed down through a robust oral tradition for tens of thousands of years. The truths in them are relevant today since they deal with those aspects of human life which never change. Hence I use them to support subjects in a paper like this one.

Above we have seen it is a non-existent snake which has created the fear in the mind of the person sitting in the half light of dawn. Understanding the power of this non-existent snake is the key to understanding how the human mind can become blinded by non-existent illusions; and hence getting closer to understanding how truth can be hidden.

The basic problem is described in the Advaita Vedanta philosophy as a mental superimposition of the image of a snake onto the rope. The mind, and hence the intellect,

believes in the superimposed image; this way the truth is covered over. It is why Vedanta often talks of 'discovering' truth; i.e. taking off the cover from that which is already there.

Another way to grasp the power of this kind of mental illusion is to give a little thought about the dreams we have prior to waking up. In dream we see images and hear sounds all projected onto the mind. In this dream state we honestly believe the events are happening to us. The sounds and images are not coming from the physical world outside. They are not provided by the working of our eyes and ears. We are completely taken in by these impressions projected onto the mind. This is what the snake in the rope means. This shows that we all have the potential to believe in falsehood through imagination.

There is one additional factor which needs to be added, it is personal mental denial.

Now we need to examine in more detail how the human mind works and is controlled so as to understand how superimpositions can create the false conclusions reached by the human intellect. Then we may become clearer in respect of those who live under illusions.

The Three Basic Modes of the Mind

The nature of the human mind is controlled by three basic qualities which are said to arise from Mother Nature; discussed further on in this section. Such is the fundamental power of these qualities that we as individuals cannot change the way the whole system works. There are many scenarios in the physical world which we may have control over as to how they work, such as the method of running a business or the way we do our shopping etc. etc. the list is endless. But the fundamental way in which the human psyche works is not within our province for change. But we can study how it works.

To clarify the above statement let us briefly examine the state of dreaming before we arrive into what we call the waking state. As stated above, there is not one person on this planet who, while in the midst of a dream, does not entirely believe that the events of that dream are really happening to them as an individual experience. This is only true while in the dream. Also when waking up all people will know that the situation of the dream was not real, when their mind compares the mental impressions of being awake with those of dreaming. Since this is true of all people we can accept it is an unchangeable part of the nature of how the human mind works and that it cannot be changed by our own efforts.

We have to accept that there is no way we can change the way it works. Hence understanding how it works may give us clues to the above power of superimposition.

A little closer comparison between dreaming and waking will reveal more of the power of the illusory 'snake in the rope'. Three fundamental aspects of the impressions we experience in the mind during dreaming are : (1) The impressions are fleeting, i.e. do not remain the same for very long; (2) They have no real substance - as with the comparison above of light and darkness; (3) They are subjective, that is we believe they are happening to us as an individual. In the waking state these three aspects do not really change. All impressions of the world around us are fleeting as we pass through each day - overtaken by new impressions arriving in a continuous stream. Also the impressions (not the world itself) have no real substance. This is revealed when in many cases we cannot remember what happened an hour or three minutes ago. Also the impressions we experience are very personal or subjective. Meaning that others do not get the same impressions that we get. This reveals something of the nature of the mind.

There is no suggestion here that there is any fault with the mind in respect of these facts, only that these are the nature of impressions in the mind. Hence in respect of these three we can conclude that there is little difference between the experience we get during dreaming and the experience while awake. This is why in both dreaming and waking we believe that what we perceive is happening to us. This is the nature of the impressions.

Furthermore, consider that impressions from imagination (the snake) can have the power to over-ride the impressions of the real world brought to us by our sense perceptions. It can be likened to viewing a scene on a cinema screen which is very pale or weak. Then another film with a stronger image is simultaneously projected onto that screen. The original scene will not be perceived. If in this case the first weak scene is the sense impressions and the stronger one is the imagination, this is what is happening with the snake in the rope. Real life is overtaken with imaginary happenings.

The above three qualities, mentioned in the first paragraph of this section, arise as modes of the way we experience the state of mind which we are in. They are (1) stillness and peace; (2) activity or constant movement; (3) inertness or lethargy. For the majority of people life is a see-saw between mainly the last two; a life of being either busy or inactive. These three are called in Sanskrit : Sattva : Rajas : and Tamas; respectively. They are clearly described in chapter 14 of the Bhagavad Gita as a guide to understanding how our psyche, and hence our whole life, is controlled by them.

Verse 9 : "Sattva attaches to happiness; Rajas to action; Tamas to shrouding and miscomprehension."

In later verses it states that these three qualities are constantly changing one for the other as we go through our daily lives. It then equates them to :- Sattva stillness and the light of intelligence; Rajas as activity, unrest and desires; Tamas as darkness, inertness, miscomprehension and delusion.

Here we see the terms 'miscomprehension' and 'delusion'. Parts of the problem we have seen above where the rope was falsely imagined as a snake.

At this point it would also be helpful for readers to embrace the subject of rebirth of the soul. Since this is also relevant if we are to fully understand how some people's psyche seems to be paralysed by false comprehension of the truth in front of them.

For those who do not already understand the concept of rebirth (sometimes called reincarnation) see the exposition of it in the section "Evidence of Reincarnation" in the paper AI v HC mentioned in the preface to this paper. There is also a practical effect of rebirth, especially in Europe, mentioned in the section "The Psychology of the Fourth Reich" in the paper "Europe - Totalitarian or Democratic". With the evidence from these two that reincarnation happens, whether we like to embrace the concept or not, we can understand that some people are inevitably born with a tendency to live a life filled with delusion. Or that, despite their best efforts, they seem to drift towards false ways.

Once again the Bhagavad Gita clarifies this for us. Chapter 14 verse 18 tells us that when a person dies with their mind enveloped in Tamas, that they will be reborn "in the wombs of the irrational". This means that it may be the influence from both the person's previous karma and the upbringing received from parents, which create a strong tendency for a person to believe in theories, opinions and beliefs, all based on ignorance.

The Bhagavad Gita also shows how Tamas (delusion) is overcome by Rajas (action) and that Rajas is overcome, or eliminated, by Sattva (mental stillness). The relevance to our investigation here is that we need to do something to remove illusions, they will not go without some action on our part. Also that for our mind to get access to the truth we need to still it so that the light of truth can show us the falseness of illusion.

These three are fundamental qualities which govern our lives; hence they merit a greater study if we are to understand how the human psyche works. Above is a brief introduction to them, since western education systems have no knowledge of them.

Power of the Non-existent Snake

We all depend on the mind to be able to gather information about the outside world. Also in dreaming sleep it is the mind which is flooded with images and sounds to fill our dreams with scene after scene. This is the condition of the dreaming mind even though the physical eyes and ears are not bringing information to the mind while we are dreaming. We are very convinced that the dream facts are happening while asleep. Yet we can have both of these conditions at the same time when we are awake and not directing our attention on the physical world around us.

Then we can have images coming to our eyes or sounds to our ears, but the presence of internal images and the sounds of our thoughts can prevent the real world from being observed; as the Brihadaranyaka Upanishad says:- Chapter 1 : Section 5: Verse 3

" 'I was absent minded, I did not see it.' 'I was absent minded, I did not hear it.' It is through the mind that one sees and hears."

This Upanishadic statement is made in view of establishing the importance of the mind over the sense organs. It does not matter if our eyes and ears are fully in working order. If the mind is not present (i.e. engaged in the world) then we will not see nor hear things coming from the material world. The Upanishad is establishing the truth that it is not through the sense organs that we see the world but through the engaged mind alone.

Most people know the situation where going to work or to do the shopping along a familiar road, that we can arrive at our destination and not have noticed any of the scenes around nor any of the sounds, while travelling along that familiar route. This can be true of any habitual or repetitive action where the person becomes absent minded. And it will always happen when a person is more attached to the inner imaginings than to the real world outside. This is partly the power and cause of mental blindness.

Hence we conclude that to gather true information of the actual situation in the world the mind needs to be free of other notions, images, imagined sounds etc. and any theories opinions or beliefs based on ignorance. If the mind is attached to any other thing than the real world, the power of the **non-existent snake** will take control of the knowledge which we believe to have arisen from the world, while we believed we were fully awake.

We can therefore also equate "the mind not being present" to be the same as the mind being so full of theories, opinions and beliefs derived from ignorance of the truth, that it is unable to become engaged in the observation of the reality presented to the senses.

Why in this document do I use the phrase, "theories, opinions and beliefs"? It is very important to fully understand the implication here. It relates to the appearance of the false snake. The snake is imagined by the mind of the observer. In this respect it is an action of

the mind of the observer. In the quote below Shankara, the great philosopher of the Advaita philosophy, made a very important statement to help us understand the nature of true knowledge and false knowledge. This quote is taken from his commentary on Brahma Sutra I.i.4. My comments are in brackets to show the relevance to our study here.

"Concentrating the mind (forming a theory, opinion or a belief - i.e. the snake) is dwelling on something mentally. Though mental, it depends on human will, and can either be done or not done or done in a different way. (True) Knowledge, on the other hand, is the result of the application of a means of valid cognition, and bears on the true nature of an already-existent object (seeing the real rope). Knowledge (of truth), therefore, does not fall within the province of what can be done, not done or done differently. It is conditioned neither by a command nor by the human will, but by the nature of an already-existent entity. Thus, even (true) knowledge is mental (like the theories, opinions and beliefs), there is a very great difference between (true) knowledge and a deliberate mental act like concentration of the mind (when forming theories, opinions and beliefs).

What is being stated here is that although they may sit side by side in the mind as being mental impressions, false knowledge and true knowledge are very different in their character due to the means by which they are arrived at. When the imagining (forming the beliefs etc.) and the act of cognition (seeing the truth) are completed, we are left with two things which could sit side by side in the mind and appear to be in opposition to each other (i.e. of similar standing). But what Shankara is saying is that there can be no opposition between false knowledge and the knowledge of the truth. It is not being able to distinguish this difference which is at the heart of **human mental blindness**.

We will see how in the later case studies how the above understanding clarifies for us what is really happening where falsehood overrides the truth of any situation.

This is how scientists with their instruments can easily make fundamental errors. The following is a clear personal example of the theory/opinion part in operation.

When I was about 16 years old (1960) I purchased a book called "1001 Questions Answered About Astronomy". Reading from the section about the planet Mars I saw the following facts reported about canals on the surface of Mars :-

"The strongest protagonist for the canals was Percival Lowell, who not only saw the canals, but saw them meeting at various junction points that he called oases, and saw them doubling at certain times in the Martian year. Others who have seen the canals have reported them variously as fairly well defined lines or as hazy and indefinable streakings."

There is also a mention in that book that the canals could only have been formed by intelligent life; and possibly for irrigation purposes.

Here it is now clear that the astronomers engaged in producing that information had superimposed onto the images from the telescope, matters which were familiar to them on this planet Earth. They were neither real nor relevant to the planet Mars.

Hence one of the first aspects of fake news came into my life in my teenage years. It is important to note here that the astronomers who made the above statements were not aware that it was fake news at that time. This may also happen at any time when a person

is convinced they are in possession of the facts, when they are not. Even so, it was actually fake news; this we now know. Because 4 years later in 1964 when the Mariner 4 had arrived at the planet Mars and had sent back to Earth the truth of the surface of Mars; it was clear from those many images that there is no surface water on the planet, let alone the possibility of canals. Also there was no evidence of intelligent life ever having been there. In fact there are actually no "well defined lines" on the surface of Mars either. So these were imagined in the minds of scientist. Images in their minds superimposed onto the facts. How often this happens even today is a matter not very well investigated.

Until that point in time, misled by a "**snake in the rope**" observation made by astronomers, I would have told others that the planet Mars had canals on its surface and possibly organic life in the form of plants etc. Also when (prior to 1964) I looked at the planet Mars through a powerful telescope, I honestly believed I was seeing canals. But in actual fact I was seeing a false image placed there by false knowledge, the ignorance based theories, opinions and beliefs of others. Because I had read fake news and believed it, false images were superimposed onto what I was actually seeing. Here we see the power of the **non-existent snake** to pass like an infection from one person to another. What is also significant here is that because those others were supposed to know more than me, the ideas in my mind became more strongly attached, through a misplaced trust in their authority. Make a note of this point here, it is very relevant to the cases studied later on.

Hence we can see that there was a compound situation of the **snake in the rope**. Firstly, my false assumption that a person with an important title was relating true facts. Secondly, that the knowledge conveyed from those facts was the actual situation. Thirdly, the fake news was reinforced by what I believed I had seen. This shows that the delusions arising from fake news, or false knowledge, can become deeply entrenched.

I hope here I have clearly shown the nature and the power of the **non-existent snake**.

Summary of Illusory Snake Factors

1. The truth of any situation can be masked or hidden by a superimposed thought.
2. Ignorance of truth is created by lack of knowledge, false knowledge or doubt.
3. The causes of ignorance are illusory since they cannot survive the test of time.
4. The darkness of illusion is removed by the light of truth.
5. Human intellect can be misled by belief in established false knowledge.
6. The quality of Tamas (miscomprehension) governs the deluded state of mind.
7. A person can be born with an established tendency to believe in false knowledge.
8. If the mind is absent (distracted) the real world will not be observed.
9. Persons in important positions are not exempt from believing in falsehoods.
10. Those who trust deluded leaders may become attached to false knowledge.

However, as mentioned above, we must not forget that human psychology is complex and can include the factor of personal denial. When the truth of a situation has finally been embraced by a person, but to fully accept it means considerable inconvenience or that their own personal image or ego would need to accept major reconfiguration, then that person may chose to personally refuse to accept some or all of the new knowledge, which they internally accept has been proved. This is not exactly the same as the snake in the rope principle working but it can be similar. It means that the person will seek other facts

which are similar to the new knowledge, which are personally easier to live with. There are many degrees of this method of embracing the realisation of a previous falsehood. Some people will totally deny all facts. Some will modify those parts which are the more uncomfortable ones. Hence each case will vary; this is why I call it personal denial.

We will see below how the above factors can be shown working in specific cases which have global significance.

Examples of the Snake in the Rope

Case Study I : The US 2020 Presidential Election

The USA is a deeply divided nation; if nation is the correct word. Why do I question this? Because it is relevant to the understanding of how belief in the falseness in the election result came about. The word '**nation**' has been traditionally used for a country which is mainly made of a single ethnic group with a common language and a single administration or government; which would include a set of laws common to all the people in the country. Also the country would have a single capital city, generally from where the government of the whole country would be administered. If religion was important in any such country, there would normally be one belief system predominant in the whole country. The USA is far from fitting this description. Why?

- A. The population of the USA is composed of many ethnic groups. Possibly a wider range of groups than any other country in the world.
- B. The first language of many groups in the USA is not English.
- C. The country is made of 50 different states, which each act like separate countries in some of the above and following factors.
- D. The above item applies to law making and government of each State.
- E. There is no single established belief system in the USA.
- F. Each State has its own justice system along with police and law courts.
- G. Each State has its own capital city.

Hence the USA is not really a nation in the traditional sense described above and is effectively 50 different countries attempting to live together as one. Therefore the word for which the letter '**U**' is in the title, is far from being true. Hence the laws and systems relating to voting in the presidential election are not the same in each State, and those people of any one State cannot necessarily understand what goes on in the other States.

As an example of the above :- I stayed with a friend in New Mexico USA. When we drove over into Colorado my friend told me that we would likely be stopped by the police because the car number plate (which had a New Mexico label) would get the police thinking we had come from outside the USA. I could not believe this statement and asked for an explanation. She said that many people in other States think that New Mexico is another country; they cannot be easily convinced that it is part of the USA. This is the kind of parochial thinking which goes on inside the USA. Not all people, but enough.

Donald Trump (D.T.) was well aware of how locally minded people are in the USA and he used this to play a game with the people in different States which were key to winning the election. As early as five months before voting started, he was using expressions such as "Rigged election" and "Voting fraud." and many other such phrases which gave rise to doubts in the minds of people all over the USA. Before anyone could have known

which way the election would have gone he began his campaign of sewing the seeds of doubt [item 2 on our 'Illusory Snake' list.] "If I loose the election it will be because it is rigged." [D.T. May 2020]. This is an unfounded accusation against the USA electoral system. 'Rig' means manipulate, falsify or mock-up. It is a very serious unfounded mental projection; for a purpose. He began to superimpose the snake image onto the rope [item 1 on our 'illusory snake ' list]. He even incited violence against senators and election officials so as to cement the illusion, which he knew he was creating so as to stay in power.

Early on D.T. knew that he was not being honest, but he also knew that there had been voting failures previously in various states, where the voting documents did not function correctly; hence doubts were already there in the minds of many people because new systems were being introduced. This way he stoked fuel into the already existing fire of doubt, knowing that many honest people would think he was right to raise these issues. This was possible because of the parochial nature of the various states and would allow for their lack of true knowledge of what was going on in other States to support the doubt.

So early on we have at least three main elements of the snake in the rope, doubt, lack of knowledge and superimposed images. The false knowledge, distorted facts of the election process, was introduced later on in the process.

D.T. also knew that there were strong subversive extremists in the USA who were pushing all manner of conspiracy theories [item 7 on the 'Illusory Snake' list above] , and had already created many 'snakes in rope' scenarios around the USA. He appealed to these groups as well, swelling the numbers of those likely rally to his support should he lose the election. This was important to him, because later on he himself began to believe the illusion. Once he had convinced himself that election was "stolen" there was no stopping him and his motley band of followers; who turned into a civil war troupe.

With doubts established, supported by true knowledge not being able to gain entry, he moved to the next stage of false knowledge. When the vote counting was still progressing he began to make false accusations of election rigging and voting fraud for which he instigated legal action. He knew that legal action would have the effect of giving belief status to his false claims; winning the legal cases was not as important as creating this effect. He knew this. The fact that he was a president gave power and credence in the minds of many to the false accusations he was making [items 9 & 10 on our 'Illusory Snake' list above]. Here we see how his cunning plan to create doubt and illusion worked.

There is no suggestion here that D.T. understood the process of "the snake in the rope", I have equated it here to show what was actually working. Also we must remember there was no legally acceptable proof of any of his claims. All of these were rejected ; not only by all reasonable honest Americans but by a wide range of State legal systems. But it was not legally winning that was important here; casting the doubt is the important factor.

Thereby the illusory snake became stronger and stronger in the minds of all those in whom doubt had already arisen and truly masked the truth [item 1 on the 'Illusory Snake' list.]. This leads naturally to the 'established illusion' [item 5 in our 'Illusory Snake' list] in the minds of the millions of people who, for a wide variety or reasons, supported D.T. by giving him their vote and hoping he would win. The hope in their minds is a key factor in

supporting the illusory nature of the false claims being made. This hope equates to the projected image of the snake; it acts as a mask to create mental blindness.

This snake cannot now be removed for millions of people in the USA because they cannot get (or do not want) access to the true knowledge [item 4 on our 'Illusory Snake' list.], which would act as the light to dispel the illusory mental darkness (or blindness).

With items 1, 2, 4, 5, 7, 9 and 10 from the 'Illusory Snake' list well established it is not surprising that D.T. was able to raise an army of supporters to fight his case for him.

We have all seen the power of the illusory "snake in the rope" working in the USA.

Let's equate the escape from this situation to an escape from the one mentioned previously of the astronomers seeing false canals on the planet Mars; by imagining we can reverse the order of the events. If the Viking 4 spacecraft had been to photograph Mars before that book was written, there would have been no mention of canals. If there were matters in that book discussing the possibility of either water or intelligent life on other planets, the Viking 4 facts would have made both of these subjects into an extremely unlikely possibility for the planet Mars. The truth of the situation would have changed the knowledge put forward in the book to be much closer to the truth. Truth, if it is acknowledged, like light over darkness, always eliminates the possibility of falsehood;

Here we can see that for the people in the USA to escape from their illusion about the election having been stolen or being fraudulent, they need the true knowledge to dawn within the minds of each person who believes in the falsehood. Until the light of truth is able to replace the illusory snake they cannot be free of the false "canals" they believe they have seen. I hope by mixing the metaphors here the difficulties surrounding the solution become clearer; showing that it is unlikely that there will ever be such truth in their minds.

Yet there is more. Such was the power of the above described illusion that the post election process was very badly disrupted. After the election result had been legitimised; legally and officially accepted, the USA began the process of what they call "The peaceful transfer of power"; by attempting to legally install the new president into the Whitehouse.

D.T. could not remove the snake illusion which he created from his own mind, such was his belief in it as the truth. He mobilised a motley mob of many thousands of people to attack the US political heart with a view to preventing the new president from being put in place. Their aims were to kill the speaker of the house and to hang the Vice President, whom D.T. had called a traitor. Here is the man who took an oath to protect the American democratic system, purposefully instigating the destruction of that same democratic institution; all powered by belief in an illusion. As the Commander in Chief of the country, the mob would certainly carry out the orders they wanted to believe he had given them. They too had been programmed by the illusory snake over several months, hence they were putty in his hands; and he knew this. He was successfully impeached for these actions before he left office as President. But the trial for the impeachment had to take place under the administration of the new president. At the beginning of that impeachment trial the prayer made asked Almighty God to "give the jurors discernment so that they will know truth from falsehood." In some way relevant to our investigation here.

The main obstacle to a successful guilty verdict was the party often designated as GOP. This stands for "Grand Old Party". This in itself is another 'snake in a rope' which I

will not examine too much here. Simply to say that the words "Grand" and "Old" carry the sense that :- 'We are the legitimate established party of the USA.' implying that the "others" are not the true upholders of the American constitution; such is the false belief in the senators who form the controlling body of that party. Hence they have stood up for D.T. with whom they strongly associate themselves. They are under such a long established snake in the rope about their own importance that they consider (as D.T. did) that they can do no wrong. Yet by almost legitimising the appalling action of their previous president they have wronged the status of the USA in the eyes of the whole world. In full view.

Let us not underestimate the power of the snake in the rope. This snake, highlighted in writings many thousands of years ago, is alive and kicking. In the face of the most overwhelming evidence the GOP remained paralysed due to their belief in illusion over and above truth. The inability of the US Senate to convict D.T. for his actions means that both the US constitution and its democracy are now broken. But not for ever - if the US legal system convicts D.T. for the illusion he created and puts him in prison for enough years to prevent him from running for president again, it is possible the people of the USA can, to some extent, restore their country's pride. They need to seriously expose the snake in the rope used by D.T. so that as many people as possible in the USA know what really happened in January 2021, and have the light of truth allowed to enter their minds.

GOP strategist Mike Murphy has stated on X (Twitter) "I really don't think Trump has the mental/intellectual rigor to distinguish between fact and fiction. He creates this avalanche of lies and then believes it because it feeds his massive ego and bottomless pit of insecurities. It's bonkers. And dangerous."

Here above are a clear examples of how the human mind can be blinded by illusion. This blindness, as with the fear of the snake, cannot go away until truth is allowed to enter. Perhaps if we rename the GOP as the Greatest Outdated Party it may help.

Understanding that the above is truly mental blindness, is a way for those who cannot understand how apparently educated, honest and intelligent people really do believe in matters which are untrue. Believing in falsehood is as the process outlined above.

Case Study II : Humans Travelling to the Moon or Mars

Let us look at the controversial subject of human interplanetary space travel; and discover the nature of the "snake in the rope" in respect of what people believe about it. I say "controversial" because many people consider it to be both too expensive and also very dangerous for those who may be sent to the Moon or Mars. The current estimate for the price of a one way ticket for single astronaut to the planet Mars is US\$ 1,500,000,000, or more than UK£2 billion; and quite a large number of space missions have failed either or both technologically and fatally for the astronauts. Approximately 67% of all rocket ventures into space, manned or unmanned, were complete failures. So maybe it could be useful to look inside the nature of this illusion, so as to discover if the time, energy and cost could be better spent; and many future human deaths avoided.

I refer back to the previously mentioned illusory canals "seen" on the surface of the planet Mars by eminent astronomers. There is another aspect to the illusion which became embedded in my mind, and I guess into the minds of millions of others. It is the science

fiction stories which were produced through various media which I read or listened to. Firstly there was series of episodes of an adventure called "Journey Into Space" produced by the BBC for the radio in 1953/54, when I was only 9 years old. As a child I listened avidly to these each week (we had no television then). It was about a group of British astronauts who first went to a base on the moon then on to Mars where they were supposed to set up a base. There were examples of other creatures living there; and many mentions of the canals on the Martian surface. In addition, and a few years later, in the boys' comic called the Eagle there was an ongoing adventure which took place on Venus and maybe other planets in the solar system. This had the effect of normalising in my mind the idea of people going from the Earth to other planets. All this science fiction reinforced the possible truth behind the false concepts about life and canals on Mars, published in the book "1001 Questions Answered About Astronomy". More fuel to the power of the illusion I was under at the time. Hence there is no doubt a strong "snake in the rope" impression lived with me, created by both illusionist and scientists; with some input from my immature psychology in which I may have hoped it was true.

The importance of this power of the media is to intensify the illusion of the idea that it can eventually become normal for human beings to hop from one planet to another and to carry on surviving in these far away places. Maybe almost as easy as hopping on a plane and going to a far off country for a holiday. Many people really began to believe this snake in a rope, especially after various science fiction story books etc. were produced.

In respect of this power of the media we must include the powerful impressions produced by the clever cinema film makers in Hollywood and other such film making studios. There is no doubt that they created a firm belief in interplanetary travel.

This later transferred to television where there have been numerous series of programmes which show humans going to very far off places; not only in the solar system but throughout the galaxy. The imagery produced is very convincing. We can equate all of these portrayals of such easy interplanetary and intergalactic travel as fake news. Those who have a rational type of intelligence may completely discard the concept of space travel; but there are a very large number of people that either hope it may become possible or simply believe what they are told. Also some people think it is part of our human evolution to eventually colonise other planets. I will come back to the subject of human evolution theory in another case study. But for now let's keep to the space travel illusion.

The most important difference in this space travel illusion compared to the previous two mentioned (canals on Mars & election fraud) is that we have a snake but no rope here. With the canals on Mars the illusion was destroyed by the facts truly discovered later. Seeing the rope in reality we knew then that there never was a snake. With the USA election fraud scenario the actual numbers counted and the failure of all the legal challenges, with the concluding judgement of the USA Electoral College are capable of removing the illusion. Hence with this evidence there is reality in the physical world which can enter like light into a dark room and take away the darkness; authenticated knowledge of the truth exposing the false knowledge as being illusion.

But with the illusion of easy interplanetary space travel we have no truth of the situation, i.e. people having failed or not at travel to other planets. If we had actual facts

from the real world this would act to either modify or destroy the illusion created. Hence without light, it is as if we are in a totally dark room with no door or window to bring in light to dispel the darkness. No true knowledge to remove the false knowledge. Therefore I cannot expect that anything written here will help to change the stance that others take, that mankind will one day "progress" into easy space travel to other planets.

Let's look a little at how we live here on Earth, so as to examine what people might need so as to live on Mars. We know our basic requirements are ample supplies of breathable air, drinkable water and food. Also in places where there are not extremes of temperature. If we look around the world and see the places where humans, over many thousands of years, have **not** established communities, we find that it is in places where these four basic requirements are **not** met. But the information we have from the instruments that have visited Mars, shows that there is no breathable air there (95% CO₂ + only traces of oxygen), neither water nor good soil for growing food. The temperatures on Mars can go down to minus 70° C. Humans could not survive at such night-time temperatures. So nobody can breathe, find water to drink or grow any food on Mars or survive at the low extremes of temperature.

If so called primitive communities here on Earth have sufficient intelligence to know that they need the above requirements so as to survive in the long term; how is it that intelligent and trained scientists have not abandoned the idea of people living on Mars? The only answer is that the snake in the rope of humans travelling to other planets is so strong in their minds they have sought to argue with many ideas that survival is possible. We will see later when I discuss the Case Study for the theory of evolution on Earth, that when any proposal is met with evidence which goes against it, the proposers, firmly attached to their proposal, make unfounded excuses to get around the problem. When their story is obviously flawed they are not truthful to the evidence. This happens because truth has been covered by illusion. They believe in the false snake ignoring the real rope.

Then there is the question of solar radiation which can kill organic life. The atmosphere on Earth protects us all from the lethal rays which come from the sun. The radiation we get is measured in units called rads. Each person is exposed to about 0.6 rads per year. Medical people say that excess beyond this (too much sunbathing) will cause cancers in the human body over some years. Astronauts on the International Space Station (ISS) get 12 times this rate (8 rads per year) during the time they are there. The exposure measured on Mars would create 33 times (20 rads) the amount we get on the earth's surface per year. Organic life cannot survive under these radiation conditions on Mars.

Add to the above the facts that Mars gravity is a little more than 1/3rd of that on Earth and the atmospheric pressure is less than 1/100th of that on earth. Our bodies are designed and develop in the gravity and air pressure which is normal around us. To take the greater part of these away will cause fairly quick deterioration in the physical structure of the whole physical organism. We can do nothing to stop this happening on Mars. Space agencies know that prolonged time spent in the environment of low gravity, high radiation causes (a) loss of bone mass. (b) loss of muscle strength including heart function. (c) the first two causing organ failure including kidney damage. (d) a large increase in

cancer risk. (e) increased risk of heart attack and stroke. Where is the hospital on Mars or the Moon? It is bordering on being criminal to send people into space.

It is clear to any intelligent person with all the above information to hand that human beings were never intended to be on such a planet as Mars. But the scientists and the promoters of space travel are suffering from human mental blindness in relation to the evidence; because their minds have been, for decades, taken over by the powerful images from the media with respect to space travel; and those of their own imaginings (canals).

If we were to take one unbiased, intelligent and knowledgeable, biologist who understands all the vital requirements needed to sustain life, and present the above facts about Mars; atmosphere with no oxygen; high solar radiation; lack of water; low gravity; extremely low air pressure; lack of fertile soil; extremes of temperature; Then pose a simple question, "Can any form of life as we know it on this planet survive under such conditions?" We all know that the answer would be an unequivocal :- "No!" Yet blind space scientists still believe they can overcome all these serious problems.

This is a powerful, and expensive, snake in a rope. They do not realise that their minds are living inside an established illusion. This is severe human mental blindness.

It is for many decades now, and in my case almost a whole lifetime, that the concept of human space travel has been portrayed in the media and has been attempted by various nations. But with possibly more than 100 serious interplanetary space rocket take-offs from this planet only seven are known to have had humans on board with the object of them putting their feet down onto a surface other than on earth. These were the seven lunar Apollo missions. One of them failed, in that an oxygen tank exploded and the mission to the moon had to be aborted. Those on board nearly lost their lives on their way back to Earth. Had they not returned alive the four following Apollo missions would likely not have happened. The six landings on the moon resulted in only 12.5 days stay.

The American space shuttle program was the nearest to the idea of a space craft leaving the earth's gravity with people on board and then landing back on earth. There were a total of 135 missions between 1982 and 2011, less than 30 years. This program was apparently a successful way of getting people, satellites, telescopes and other equipment into earth orbit. But these missions were never intended to leave earth orbit. There were two complete disasters where in 1986 the Challenger shuttle broke apart on launch killing all onboard. Years later the Columbia shuttle disintegrated when attempting to land back on earth; again killing all onboard. It is now ten years since the last shuttle mission; the program has been suspended since then. The harsh realities of going to space had been witnessed. Maybe some aspect of a rope to remove the snake had appeared.

We can assume that the two space shuttle fatal disasters did bring in an aspect of the "rope" saviour to the "snake" of easy space travel. Here was a truth that the human race had to accept. The only space craft, which resembled in any way those shown on the Hollywood and other media illusions, had failed. Meaning that easy space travel, which had lived in the minds of many people for decades, was shattered to some extent. It was these two failures of the shuttles which began the decline in interest of the idea of space travel. Leading to the space shuttle program closure in 2011. Currently there is far less public support in the USA for the idea of people going on space craft to the planet Mars.

Hence it seems that the illusion of easy space travel has come and partly departed over a period of more than half a century. Although there are many younger people who have aspirations of becoming astronauts and of travel to the moon and Mars. Their minds are taken over by the video games and other clever graphics created within computer programs especially where travel in space craft are part of the illusion created. Few younger people realise that all such computer graphics are entirely a snake in the rope illusion (without the reality of a rope); as are all films produced by Hollywood and other media outlets. Hence they really believe that films, television and computer graphics are a representation of what can happen in the real world; and they are duped to believe in space travel. They too do not have the reality of a rope to dispel their illusory snake.

The USA current national debt is more than US\$ 26.5 trillion. Resulting in interest payments of at least US\$ 53 billion each year. This is five times the debt at the turn of the century. The cost to their economy is almost unbearable and with the cost of the 2020 pandemic will only increase at possibly a higher rate than before. The main question is :- can the people of the USA continue to support the spending of US\$20 billion each year, on the space program, when the country has such a high burden of debt? In the last 60 years the USA has spent US\$ 900 billion on the space program. And 60 years ago some of those dollars were worth much more than the recent ones. This is the cost of the space snake in the Mars rope for the USA. That money could have been used to alleviate all US poverty.

Also too many lives have been already lost chasing this illusion. And we do not know how many people have had their health permanently damaged due to either or both mental stress and excessive exposure to solar radiation (ISS visits). Is it now time to wake up from the space dream and begin to face the reality? Can this awakening happen?

The answer to this is probably 'no!' because now, in order to show that they can be as great as the USA, such countries as India, China and Japan have joined Europe and Russia by creating an ambitious space program. These countries really believe that space travel is human progress. This creates a political space race, which is costing nations enormous sums of tax payers hard earned cash. When will the dream end? Not in my life time I am sure. If the human race could honestly use the intelligence with which it is endowed it should be able to see that Mars (or any other planet and the moon) is not the place to go.

Interlude

Let's recap so far. It may be useful to review the various factors which contribute to our human mental blindness. Here is a summary of the factors which we have seen so far. With one or two we have not seen, but are also common causes of false beliefs.

i. Miscomprehension - where due to external factors the person is unable to gather the correct sense impressions, such as the darkness where the rope is.

ii. Previous misinformation where a person has assumed that information given was accurate and reliable when it was not - e.g. the canals or intelligent life on Mars.

iii. Deliberate covering of facts. Here we can include the action of denial where for various reasons a person cannot or will not accept the evidence available. Random facts may be introduced to serve this aim.

iv. Distortion of evidence - here one trusted influential person distorts information to their followers to further a specific aim or intended outcome; as happened in the 2020 US presidential election.

v. Opinions of other influential people - the example being that several astronomers claimed they had seen canals on Mars - influencing other astronomers, and readers of books portraying such false facts.

vi. The power of the media. We all know that Hollywood and other powerful media companies did not intend to mislead but only to entertain. But the illusions created are a side effect of entertainment.

vii. Attachment to previous attractive concepts. e.g. Space scientists having grown up with space illusions, cannot give up the idea of humans surviving on Mars. Their hope that it is true, masks the facts.

viii. Established theories - where unproven postulations have become mainstream. Such unwitnessed things as the origins of the solar system or the planets, or the origins of life on earth.

ix. Fake news - which is similar to 'iv' above but with the added dimension of the false knowledge leading to conspiracy theories.

Our remedies to the above ignorance or delusion are basically three in number.

I. The individual remembers previous true knowledge of the situation.

II. Another person informs the deluded individual of the true situation.

III. The light of the truth of the situation becomes available to the individual.

Note here the word 'individual' . With all snake in the rope situations it is each person that needs to realise the truth. Even if facts or knowledge are broadcast to whole nations, each individual will not lose the illusion unless one of the three above finds its target.

In all cases we are dealing with a none existent snake. Yet we have seen that its removal can be a very difficult and tricky task for all concerned. How can a non-existent illusion have such power? It relates to a basic principle which is how we all became individual people. Which I will not deal with at this point; but later I may do.

With this review in mind, let's look at a few other cases of 'snake in the rope'.

Case Study III : An Effective Remedy for the Covid 19 Pandemic

This case shows more than one "snake in a rope" scenario acting in combination.

There are many ways to deal with the need for a human being to resist the onslaught of a virus attack on its health. All of those which are most effective do the same thing; they boost or assist the human immune system to beat off the attack. Healthy human beings mostly have the capacity to resist the infections inflicted on them by Mother Nature. If this were not the case there would not be a human race on this planet. In the worst case scenario, such as the highly contagious Black Death pandemic in the 14th century, many millions of people died (maybe 50% of Europe's population) from the attack by a pathogen for which they had little or no resistance; yet the populations of all countries affected survived and continued to increase. This shows that sufficient numbers were able to fight off the vicious attack; and that their immune systems were able to deal

with it. We do not know how the infection was made to recede. But many things were not documented; including the value of natural plant medicines which, in those times, were the main means by which ill health matters were dealt with. So normal were these methods that it was not deemed important to record the use to which they were put. But we do know that the infection was dealt with and life came back to normal soon after. Recurrence of the Black Death came as near as the 19th century, but not as wide spread. In recent times antibiotics have been used to combat it (i.e. it is not a virus).

For more, easy to read, information of the power of the human immune system see my paper entitled, "UK Covid-19 - Deaths in the Elderly" in the section "Getting and Keeping a Good Immune System". Important for all to read to maintain good health.

For more details of plant medicines, see my presentation to the City of London Pensioners' Association in 2017 at the City of London Guildhall; paper entitled "Home Remedies." In that paper I show how effective they can be when carefully used.

Modern times have veered towards the use of more laboratory methods of dealing with the viral infections, mainly due to the idea that nobody should die from disease. The discovery that the human immune system can be supported against a specific virus by subjecting it to a weakened strain of the virus (vaccination), has changed the way that the health of those with weakened immune systems can be improved. The first vaccine was for smallpox developed more than 200 years ago. But vaccines only help to boost the human immune system. To work effectively they rely on a well tuned immune system to develop appropriate antibodies soon after the vaccination. After that there is no vaccine material in the human blood stream. They do not themselves actually get involved in the battle. Whereas antibiotics actually kill bacteria and need to be continuously administered during the time of infection. They are however ineffective against viruses.

There are several "snake in the rope" episodes related to covid-19. Some are about the virus itself, others are about the vaccines. Many ordinary people have doubts about vaccines in general. One part of the illusion of the snake [remember (1) absence of knowledge, (2) false knowledge or (3) doubt]. There are many people who will not accept vaccines for children, because links have been made with such things as autism appearing in children; especially after being inoculated with multiple function vaccines such as the MMR which is for mumps, measles and rubella. These claims have never been successfully refuted by the health authorities. As we say, the jury is still out on such issues. All this adds to the doubts surrounding covid-19 vaccines. Hence it is not difficult for fake news to gain a hold through social media and put fear into the minds of many. Once false knowledge of vaccines gets a hold there is little that can be done to remove the illusions in the minds of people. Some have religious reasons. Some UK front line medical staff, helping to fight the horrors of covid-19 every day, have refused to be vaccinated, due to the snake in the rope of the many stories told about vaccines. Some listed below.

- i. The vaccine will change our DNA, making us genetically modified.
- ii. The vaccine will implant a microchip into our arm, so we can be tracked.
- iii. A person injected with the covid vaccine has died.

- iv. Microsoft founder Bill Gates believes thousands of people will die after having been injected with a covid vaccine.
- v. The Spanish flu vaccine killed 50 million people.

All such false information put around the internet and other media has deterred many thousands of people from accepting a vaccine. Hence the reality is that their lives are actually in more danger as a result of the projection of these false images into people's minds.

I. To alter the DNA of even a plant is a long and complex process. It cannot be done with ½ ml of vaccine liquid.

II. There currently is no microchip which will pass through the fine tube of an inoculation needle; which is 0.5 millimetre.

III. The person who was supposed to have died, later gave a TV interview to prove he was still alive.

IV. Bill Gate's words relating to how many may suffer side effects were transposed into a number who might die.

V. At the time of the Spanish flu there were no vaccines available to fight it.

So here are five illusory snakes followed by five real ropes to dispel the illusions. But those who have no access to the truth or are prone to believe what they hear or read, will have these illusions impressed on their minds, with less chance of removing the doubt.

But the more important snake in the rope about this pandemic is the one relating to the use of traditional plant remedies; where the facts about the use of a herbal remedy have been ignored. This is the subject of part of my paper "**UK Covid 19 Deaths in the Elderly.**" Readers may need to read that part of the paper (addenda 1 & 2 from page 19).

There is a huge snake in the rope about using herbal medicines. This has come about through several factors over centuries; which I will briefly describe here.

In the Middle ages in Europe, most people's life was under the control of the Holy Roman Empire (HRE). This was a very strict religious control. The same psychology which Donald Trump has was prevalent in the religious leaders all those centuries ago. As with D.T. they believed they were right in all they thought and they believed they could do no wrong. And just like D.T. they did not want to lose control of the people. Hence their regime was to execute all those who went against them. Exactly what the followers of D.T. tried to do on January 6th 2021. Anyone called heretic by the HRE was executed without a fair trial. Europeans have not been such nice people in previous centuries.

But a hidden (mainly undocumented) agenda which the religious leaders had was to eliminate what they considered to be un-Christian; the practices of foetus abortion and contraception. This was being covertly carried out across the whole of Europe; and had been probably going on before the Christians took over the scene. It was done by those very knowledgeable and skilled physicians who used herbal methods. There are several herbs which can trigger an abortion; likewise with contraception. Traditionally those who knew how to do this were naturally the ladies in the community, since these things were mainly ladies business. The (so called) Christian investigators who were charged with eliminating this practice used a false accusation against those women by calling them evil

witches. Millions of women across Europe were burnt at the stake. Some reports say that villages or towns had only two or three women remaining after the holocaust of witches.

This was the beginning of the snake in the rope about herbal medicine practice. Although herbal medicine continued, there was an inevitable stigma attached to it. Not least that if anyone is caught they may be executed. Herbal practice gained a bad reputation. This was a projected and false concept; which has remained in the minds of British people for centuries; and has never fully gone away.

Moving to the 18th & 19th centuries we had a period of time in the UK where medical practice, being unregulated, began to attract many false doctors with mystical wonder cures. These false doctors were called quacks (taken from a Dutch term). Records of the UK Parliament have more than 1,000 remedies offered; most of which were false or ineffective. Hence the snake in the rope against true and valuable herbal medicine was reinforced due to actual false remedies acting as a kind of rope to the original illusion about natural plant medicines.

When so called science based medicines began to dominate the scene, the opinions about alternative cures, although very effective, became worsened. Science has become the magic wand in the minds of most Europeans. It carries the sense that it is a perfect irrefutable thing. But as we have seen in this paper, it also has falsehood within it.

Add to the above in this 21st century the relentless propaganda against herbal cures from the huge pharmaceutical companies and we can easily see that a huge snake in the rope has become part of the official opinion in the minds of most UK medical practitioners. There are many good reasons to doubt alternative remedies; but those that have been successfully used for thousands of years should not be wrongfully condemned. Unfortunately this is the case with many modern doctors.

Now let's see the relevance of all this to the covid-19 remedy.

A plant called *Artemisia Annu* has been used for more than a thousand years to deal with sicknesses which arise from pathogens. The World Health Organisation (W.H.O.) approved its use as a remedy against malaria in 2001. There are three main types of malaria trypanosome. The interesting comparison is that there are three modern scientific remedies required for malaria; as each one can only be designed to work against a single pathogen. *Artemisia* is effective against all three strains. This power it has can also be applied to virus attacks.

A French based company in Madagascar has been extracting artemisinin from this plant for some decades now and using it in many remedies against African diseases. It was used against the SARS virus outbreak and also against Ebola. Even though modern science based vaccines are very effective, we know that the covid-19 pandemic could not be treated with any existing vaccines in the early months of 2020. Because these previous vaccines were designed to be effective against one specific virus. New vaccines needed to be developed. *Artemisia Annu* was already tested and effective in 2001; 19 years earlier.

Unfortunately for hundreds of thousands of people who have died from covid-19, the W.H.O. have become strongly influenced by the snake in the rope illusion against herbal cures which I described above. Hence when the President of Madagascar announced at the beginning of the pandemic, that his country would beat covid-19 with *Artemisia*, the

world was coerced by the W.H.O. to ignore it as an untested remedy. An irrelevant and untrue statement. A thousand of years of effectiveness does not need further proof for a medicine which is safe.

Let's look at the evidence of covid 19 numbers provided by the W.H.O.

Country	Date	Total cases	Total deaths	Population
UK	25/03/20	9,529	465	68,017,319
	09/04/20	65,077	7,978	
	30/11/20	989,000	46,240	
	20/02/21	4,105,675	120,365	
Madagascar	25/03/20	19	0	27,946,942
	09/04/20	93	0	
	30/11/20	608	243	
	20/02/21	19,598	292	
The large increase in cases from 11/20/to 02/21 for both may be related to increased testing.				

It is clear these numbers speak for themselves; that Madagascar's use of the Artemisia herbal remedy has proved to be very effective.

The most important knowledge which this reveals to us is that in the UK and in many countries across the world, many thousands of people have died unnecessarily due to the snake in the rope illusion. This was partly caused by so called authoritative people in the W.H.O. guided more by the opinions of the western scientific community than their own human intelligence. If the W.H.O. had endorsed the use of Artemisia for covid-19 in the same way they approved it for malaria in 2001, we cannot know how many countries would have tried it while they were waiting for the development of vaccines. The W.H.O. knew it was harmless; they had nothing to lose. This is such a large mistake made by the world, that it can never be accepted. The W.H.O. acted hypocritically over this issue.

Also we should wake up to the fact that new variants of the covid-19 virus are appearing all the time. We do not know when the vaccines people have been treated with will no longer be effective. Whereas it is almost certain that Artemisia will continue to assist people to resist all strains of the virus and for them to avoid being hospitalised.

This is the power of human mental blindness to damage fellow human beings.

See the Addendum for the April 2021 update related to the South African variant of covid 19 on page 38.

Case Study IV : Darwin's Theory of Evolution

As with the previous case, here there are multiple snake in the rope scenarios; all created by Charles Darwin to support his false "snake" idea.

We should note the use of the word "theory" here. This is how it is normally termed. In this modern materialistic and scientific era there are many such postulations which carry the main title "theory". Examples are "The Theory of Atoms "; "The Big Bang Theory" of the origin of the Universe; and so on. I believe the title "theory" applies because they are subjects which have not been witnessed; at least not fully and truly witnessed. Atoms are impossible to witness due to their, apparently, being so small. The beginning of the Universe by its very nature is also impossible for anyone to witness.

This whole subject of removing the illusory snake is about, "*--- the application of a means of valid cognition, and bears on the true nature of an already-existent object. ---*" as described in the quote from Adi Shankara above. This means witnessing reality with human consciousness. Hence if a subject is not witnessed, it is titled "theory", and could be a "snake in a rope". Those concepts not witnessed need to be explained with ideas.

In my early teenage years I took a deep interest in palaeontology. I went all over the South of England UK visiting old disused quarries, seaside cliffs, clay pits, sand pits etc. All the places where it was known that plenty of fossils could be found. Eventually I had a large collection of fossils, housed in an uncle's house; who it was that took me to all those places. I studied the geological strata of the South of England from books. But generally the knowledge of the time-line and the different ages to which the many strata related, was not called a theory. This was because it related to matters which many people had observed. The knowledge came from looking at the "rope", not guessing about any "snake". Those other things called 'theory', mentioned above, are involved with illusory snakes in ropes.

Hence it is correctly called "Darwin's *Theory* of Evolution." And as with those other theories mentioned above, it came from an idea or an image in the mind of one man. Hence it is a good candidate for our study of human mental blindness. As we have seen, mental images can be very convincing; and can completely take over the truth of any situation. It is the power of these mental imaginings which we need to notice more.

Darwin was interested in the creatures and plants of nature. His well known trip across the world on a merchant ship, the H.M.S. Beagle, took him to the Galapagos Islands. On one of the islands he observed more than a dozen varieties of finches. Studying their differences and similarities, the idea that they may all be related to each other in some way, popped into his mind. Here was the arrival of his "snake", projected onto the many 'finch-ropes'. He thought a lot about this idea, as he describes in his treatise "Origin of Species" (O.o.S). The more he thought about it the stronger the image of the snake became. This is the nature of the human mind which we have already studied with D.T.'s election; also the absurd idea of people going to live on Mars, in the minds of deluded scientists. Those in whom the illusion has remained over some time become convinced of the falsehood; and attached to it. This happens because the real rope is not accessible to them; then their psyche is paralysed by attachment to self imposed illusion.

However, Darwin was also interested in palaeontology; hence he was well aware of the findings to date at the time he lived (mid 19th Century). He also knew that there was a contest between the religious types and the scientific types in the UK; who had a wide chasm between their concepts of how the universe, including mankind and all the creatures, came into existence. Even in modern times there is a contest between the scientists and the creationists; mainly about the same subject with the same chasm.

Darwin's idea of the origin of all life is that at some time in the (un-witnessed) past, all life on earth came from a common source. Meaning perhaps, that all current creatures may have a common origin in tiny bacteria living in water. It is clearly shown in his treatise (O.o.S) with a diagram - part of which appears below.

In the book the diagram is wider. Showing more vertical lines up to the letter L on the right side. The horizontal time-lines are labelled with Roman letters from I to XIV. The diagram seems to imply that all vertical lines converge on an undeclared common life form. But this convergence is not fully shown. Here it is clear that Darwin was indicating that various existing species originated from common ancestors. This is the general idea which is taught to children in school, almost as if it is a true fact. It is disingenuous for education systems to teach it in this way. We are not being honest to our children. It is only a theory; never really proved. Yet modern ideas of evolution show a similar diagram linking species in this way; none of them are proved to be true.

The more Darwin worked up his theory of how the finches may all be varieties or may have "evolved" from a single species, two things were going on in his mind, which he describes in his treatise. One was that the theory, if it applied to finches, must therefore apply to all other creatures including plants. The second thing was about how he could get this theory accepted past all the objections he might have back in the UK. These objections would come from geologists, scientists and palaeontologists and also the religious types. On board the H.M.S. Beagle, on his way back, he had plenty of time to mull over his ideas and work out how he would prove he was right. His snake grew stronger and stronger; as did his personal attachment to his own (illusory) mental idea.

His way of dealing with these difficulties was to bring more "illusory snakes" into the theory. This he had to do because there was not enough evidence to prove his idea of one species slowly changing over many thousands of years (maybe millions) into other similar looking creatures. Below are a few of Darwin's "difficulties" raised in his treatise (O.o.S). They show what an intelligent person he was; and how clever he was at his cover up. (1 & 2 are on page 207; 3, 4 and 5 are on page 208)

1. "Why, if species have descended from other species by fine gradations, do we not everywhere see innumerable transitional forms?"

2. "Why is not all nature in confusion, instead of the species being, as we see them, well defined?"

3. "Is it possible that an animal having for instance, the structure and habits of a bat, could have been formed by the modifications of some other animal with widely different habits and structure?"

4. "Can we believe that natural selection could produce, on the one hand, a tail of a giraffe, on the other hand an eye?"

5. "As by this theory innumerable transitional forms must have existed, why do we not find them embedded in countless numbers in the crust of the earth?"

These are just a few of the many problems his theory gave him to answer. The idea of 'natural selection' is an important part of Darwin's theory; it is a key for his clever ideas to cover up the snake in the rope. In his book he calls it "The Theory of Natural Selection". So we can apply all the points about the term "theory" as we have above. He himself used this idea which has no real origin in fact. It is really another snake in a rope. In Chapter IV Darwin equates natural selection to be "Survival of the Fittest". It is based on creatures not being able to survive unless they adapt to external changing conditions such as climate, terrain, predators or availability of food etc. As if they use some undefined intelligence and ability to modify the form or structure of their bodies to suit the changing environment around them. This ability would be truly astonishing and would begin to equal the mystic powers said to be available to some accomplished yogis, who live in the Himalayas. If creatures had this ability they would also have the ability to give birth to a completely different species from within themselves at will; - this unlikely ability in itself might have solved some of Darwin's problems. But he does not see it in that way. Or he knew there were limits on his revolutionary ideas.

There can truly be no such thing called "natural selection" because changes in the form of an animal, as we now know, involves changes to the DNA of creatures. This claim of his is similar to the 'canals on Mars' scenario followed by the Marina 4 discovery. Later real information which cancelled the previous 'theory', thought to be fact. If Darwin had known about the controlling nature of DNA, he could not have come up with the idea of natural selection. Because he would need to explain how any creature could have control of its DNA. Which we know is not a natural possibility. Animals do not have access to complex laboratory methods to be able to decide on the DNA of their future offspring.

Since the changes to species could not be the magical conscious change, mentioned above; it must therefore be a mutation or an accidental change; which would not achieve any sense of organised design which could deal with environmental requirements, which Darwin claims is the driving force for natural selection. In his book he enumerates the many objections to the theory of natural selection current in his time. Most of those objections are still current in the minds of naturalists. He deals with each one using spurious argument not honestly backed up with long term study and proof.

So it is clear that Darwin was behaving a bit like Donald Trump. When he knew he was defeated he began to invent ideas, such as natural selection, which could prove he

was right. Such ideas which if the truth were known, they are more illusions piled on the original one to get his own way. Darwin, like D.T., was convinced he was right. Most human beings suffer from the same psychology to some extent, at times during their life.

The other clear example of a "snake in the rope" justification of his evolution theory revolves around item 5 on the above list of Darwin's "difficulties"; the non-existence of fossil evidence. This was his greatest difficulty and he knew it. All he needed was sufficient evidence from fossils that there was a geological record showing the gradual change from one species to another. Then he would not have needed to say all the other things which were all justifications for his theory. But such record had not been found in his time; nearly two hundred years ago. The same is true today. There is no evidence; which is the rope to dispel his very obvious snake. So what does he propose? Yet another snake in another rope. Most of the text in "Origin of Species" is justifying all the objections which he knew would come from others.

In chapter X of his book (O.o.S) he tackles the above difficulty by saying that the geological record is imperfect. What he means is that over time much of the evidence has been eroded by nature. Lost for all time, so that we can't find the evidence. At least we can say that D.T. blamed others for stealing the election; those who could answer back with evidence to the contrary. Darwin was cleverer than D.T. He blamed Mother Nature for stealing the evidence of fossils. She cannot answer back. He does not explain how Mother Nature knew which types to erode from the rock deposits, so that the particular evidence, which he would need in the future, would be removed. His whole idea of an imperfect geological record is preposterous. It is one of his many spurious cover-ups. The action of a man desperate to prove he was right.

One single proof is enough to show that Darwin was prone to justify and cover up. And it shows the disingenuous approach he had in his method of problem solving. Brilliant he was. Honest he was not.

His idea is wrong because, where he says that the evidence of many thousands of years (or even millions) which would have shown the transitional species, has been struck from the record. In the UK alone there is a record of the Cretaceous rock spanning continuously 35 million years; with the Jurassic record topping out at 185 million years of continuous record. In all these layers of rock there is no evidence of what Darwin calls "transitional species". So there goes another torpedo into the ship of Darwin's theory. I think the ship is sunk now; although there are a number of other snakes which he introduced, which I will not take up more space with here. Showing more than once that he was devious in this way, is enough to undermine his whole approach to the subject and his overall theory. Read his book and decide for yourself.

Yet in many people's minds there is still the question of how can there be so many species? How can all the different life forms appear? We know that cross breeding mixes the DNA of dogs for example. The same is true of horses, sheep, cows and many others. Also we know that cross pollination of plants can create new varieties. So nature, assisted by humans, does have its own way of changing the species scene. And over millions of years we can conclude that this may have happened in many ways and many times. As to

"survival of the fittest" I am sure there is something in this idea which is always true. But this doesn't mean it is the cause of the origin of species in the way Darwin describes.

As to the arrival of each type in the first place we need to know a little more about how life forms arise. This is too large a subject for this paper; simply to say that it is not the province of the physical world. If readers have looked at my article AI v HC then the subject of consciousness is the key to the answer. There I have stated that consciousness pervades all things and that when soul enters any life situation, intellect begins to work. It is from this Divine aspect of consciousness working with intellect, which is limitless in what forms it can create in the physical world. But as I said above - it is too large a subject at this point; I may touch on it at the end of this paper. In our materialistic age the concept of the control or creation of the physical coming from the unseen spirit within, is generally not accepted in the minds of most. Vedanta, however, does record spontaneous creation of life forms through Nature.

So to sum up Darwin's theory; we can see that the rope-snake appeared in his mind, and as with the space travel example, he could not find a real-rope (truthful knowledge) so that the snake could be either proved or dispelled, even for himself. If he had been more concerned about the requirement for truthful evidence, than he was for becoming a leader of ideas, he would not have gone against the evidence which disproved his idea.

We have seen with the US election illusion, that there maybe generations of Americans who will continue to believe the 2020 election was actually stolen. The same it is with Darwin's theory. Across the world, since the original acceptance of the theory, his well established snake has continued to delude many to believe in it. This means that practically the snake illusion is planted in their minds and, unknown to them, it changes what they see when studying matters of fossils, species etc. Just as I thought I saw canals on Mars caused by a previous idea. This happens, as it did in my case, because of the misplaced belief in the authority of other people. Not in the people, but in their supposed authority. This paper has shown that eminence in the worldly sphere does not exempt any person suffering from a situation where their ideas, policies, theories etc. are based on illusion. Hence for at least the whole of last century anthropologists, palaeontologists, naturalists and many others who study life forms have used the word "evolved" in the Darwinian sense. Believing it to be true without any real evidence that during all those unwitnessed millennia such evolution has taken place. We should bow down to the power of the snake in the rope type of illusion; and wake up to how much of our thinking is dominated by it, even on a daily basis.

Epilogue

Earlier I sort of promised I would open the deeper side to this snake in the rope. Also at the end of Case Study II, it was stated, "*It relates to a basic principle which is how we all became individual people.*" where I also said I might later go into this side of the subject.

Really, the true knowledge behind this is the main purpose of the "snake in the rope" scenario as used in the Advaita Vedanta philosophy; and behind this paper.

Let's briefly recap in another way. If readers have grasped the essence of this paper, it is really showing us that images, ideas or theories have great power over what happens in

the physical world. Non-existent, immeasurable, weightless things that imaginings are, have shown us that they can cause the insurrection of thousands of people to storm and break into the government building of a major democracy. These ungraspable things in the minds of people can cause powerful complex machines to be created and sent to distant planets. Due to one man's imagination, perhaps millions of people really believe the noble creature that the human being is, has evolved from a less capable and far less intelligent creature such as an ape. Have we really grasped the power of mental images through reading this paper? For this is its title "Human Mental Blindness."

Pause and reflect on the above power of images in the mind, for a minute or two.

===== pause for thought =====

If any reader has begun, even a little, to see the power that the mind has over all that we do in life, this may be the first step into understanding what a human being really is.

Due to the power that the mind has to project illusion, deeply within our psyche we have projected the false concept that we (the human being) are our physical body only.

In another way, those who say "my body" and hence have a sense that there are two entities in play (me and my body) have projected the image of the body onto the soul.

This is what Vedanta calls "mutual superimposition". This in a strange way means that we have projected the immortality of the soul onto the physical body.

And conversely we have projected the temporary nature of the physical body onto the eternal nature of the soul that dwells within. A kind of double incompatible projection.

This is the meaning behind, "basic principle of how we all became individual people"; mentioned earlier.

This mutual superimposition results in the double concept whereby, people cannot get any real daily sense that their body will ever die. But they believe that when the physical body does eventually die that the whole human being will die; there is nothing after death. It is under this normal daily double delusion that we live our lives.

This is what is meant by the term "mutual superimposition" and the analogy of the snake in the rope scenario has been designed to open up an investigation into this.

It is the reason why we tend to believe in imagined things or projections onto the mind. Because we consider ourselves to be an individual arising from original projection.

The aim of the Vedanta system of thought is to show us this illusion. The knowledge in the writings come from enlightened people who have clearly seen it working.

Let's not project any idea (snake) that because Vedanta deals with the subject of the human soul, that it is anything to do with religion.

Some people in modern times equate Vedanta with Hinduism. The truth is that the writings of the Vedanta philosophy pre-date the arising of Hinduism by several millennia. Yet it is true that many Vedantic concepts are to be found in Hinduism. We should not be surprised that profound subjects dwelling side by side on the same sub-continent will mean the younger one is influenced by the older one. Vedanta is not a religion. The Vedanta writings were formed particularly for the kind of world we are now living in. A world where personal ideas and interests can override the welfare of others, and mask truth with falsehood.

Consider the similarities in relation to impressions mentioned earlier when in the states of waking or dreaming. Also there is the deep sleep state. Many people will say, "I had a very good and deep sleep last night." This shows there is some observation going on even then; although we do not seem to be fully aware of it when we wake up.

From the Brihadaranyaka Upanishad Section IV.iii.23

"There is no break in the vision of the witness for it is imperishable."

Anyone who reviews their experience reflectively in relation to these three states of life, will notice that the same Self, or observer, is present all the time without a break. Yet those three states of deep sleep, dreaming sleep and waking, being mutually exclusive, give way to each other in a cycle each day. Hence it is possible to observe that our True Self is different from those three states. I can confirm to all readers from experience, that this conscious Self will not cease to be present even after leaving the current body.

Above I touched on the three modes of the way the mind works and introduced the three Gunas or qualities. Western education seems to have ignored these fundamental aspects of how life and the world around us is organised. These three Gunas are what Nature is. They have far reaching effects. In the Shri Bhagavad Gita it states this clearly: Chapter 18 verse 40.

"There is no entity on Earth, or again in heaven among the Devas (Angels and celestial beings), that is devoid of these three Gunas born of Mother Nature."

This being the case, how has modern education not included this wisdom? The answer is that modern science is lost in the dream (snake in the rope) of everything being the physical world, without looking to see what really organises it all behind the scenes. We have seen in this paper how the unseen mind controls the physical world. We need to extend this vision to the creation of all things. Consider the diagram below and join it up with other portrayals I have given in this and other papers.

Here we can see the Gunas in action; and that space (ether) has the nature of stillness; fire the nature of movement and action; earth the nature of fixity and inertia. The same qualities can be applied to Soul, Mind and Body respectively. Those items between the three carry a combination of the qualities on either side. We cannot deny that this is the case. It is how the world works. Because our education system has not included the Gunas, we are not denied the chance to find out for ourselves. My school did not teach astronomy or palaeontology.

Studying these three qualities in this way will help to clarify some of the mysterious statements made in this paper and other papers I have presented. They can also be applied to the three states of deep sleep, dreaming sleep and waking. This is how all

encompassing they are. As verse 40 above states : "There is no entity which is devoid of these three."

Let me give the last words here to this most well known of Vedanta scriptures - the Shri Bhagavad Gita.

The central character, the Lord Shri Krishna, is known to have been the Creator of this universe who came in human form to impart a wisdom, which will become immortal and will serve the whole human race for all time. This has been shown to be the case.

The words below give us insight into how the threefold nature of the human mind actually works when under the power of one or other of the three qualities. Also called the three Gunas in Sanskrit (if needed review their description above on page 7). If the following verses are read in relation to the thrust of this paper, it will be seen how it came about that the events arising in the above case studies do what they do to our ways of living and thinking. These words give guidance for understanding both actions and the one who carries them out (the agent) and how the mind controls the two. They are the highest wisdom of mankind.

Also these words can help us to see a little deeper into ourselves. Shri Bhagavad Gita is for the benefit of all people. The text is taken from Chapter 18 verses 23 to 28.

An action which is ordained, which is free from attachment, which is done without (being affected by the emotions of) love or hatred by one not desirous of the fruit (results), that action is declared to be controlled by Sattva.

But that action which is done by one craving for desires, or again with egoism, or with much effort, that is declared to be controlled by Rajas.

That action which is undertaken from delusion, without heed to the consequence (to others), loss, injury and ability, that is declared to be controlled by Tamas.

An agent who is free from attachment non egoistic, endued with firmness and zeal and unaffected by success or failure, is controlled by Sattva.

Passionate, desiring to obtain the fruit (results) of action, greedy, cruel, impure, moved by joy and sorrow such an agent is said to be controlled by Rajas.

Unsteady, vulgar, stubborn, deceitful, malicious, indolent, despondent, procrastinating such an agent is controlled by Tamas.

The Lord Shri Krishna

Now from Chapter 14, which teaches all about the Gunas (three qualities) vv 18 & 20. Here it is clear that it is the power of the mind under the control of the Gunas, which is the cause of both the evolution of the human body and the way our lives will go.

Those who are fixed in Sattva go upwards (progress spiritually); the Rajasic remain in the middle; and the Tamasic, (those) abiding in the functions of the lowest Guna, go downwards (perhaps being born as an animal in their next life).

The embodied one having crossed over (become detached from) these three Gunas, out of which the body is evolved, is freed from birth, death, decay and pain, and attains to immortality. - - - - - The Lord Shri Krishna

END OF PAPER

APRIL 2021 ADDENDUM - COVID 19 VARIANTS

This addendum is necessary in respect of the impact of the South African variant of the covid 19 virus, which has impacted on the Madagascan island and their use of Artemisia Annua as a covid 19 remedy. Their use of Artemisia Annua has been undermined.

South Africa, along with other countries which have malaria problems, have always used Artemisia Annua derivatives to treat malaria and other respiratory diseases. This included the epidemic of SARS in the early 21st century. Hence their intervention treatment of covid 19 used two compounds produced by western styled pharma-ceutical companies which are derived from Artemisia Annua. These are (1) Artesunate-amodiaquine and (2) Pyronaridine-artesunate. These substances have been approved by WHO. It is most likely that the commercial production of these has involved a chemical synthesis of the derivatives.

As we know all viruses have the ability to mutate and survive any attempt to eliminate them. Covid 19 is no exception. It would appear that the use of the two Artemisia Annua derivatives along with other intervention medications has caused a covid 19 variant to develop which was first identified in South Africa; now called the South African variant.

Due to the variant arising under the use of the artesunate drugs used in South Africa, this covid 19 variant developed a resistance to the Artemisia Annua treatment used by the Madagascan people. Hence their use of the herbal remedy has had to be reviewed.

This shows that the western idea that substances can be replicated from herbal remedies by chemical synthesis can produce damaging side effects. Damaging that is the traditional use of herbal remedies. The two systems of medicine should not be mixed in this western way, as the outcome which has been shown above cannot be predicted or avoided.

The western based comments on this have erroneously stated that the Madagascan use of Artemisia Annua was not successful. But these comments do not include all the knowledge behind the effect of the South African variant as stated above.

END OF ADDENDUM

The beauty you see in the world comes from Him who exists within you.
Without His presence within, you would not see anything, even that beauty.

First know that your-Self is Him, then no one thing will seem to be
more beautiful than any other thing. You will know that He is all things.

Then you have true Self-knowledge. This is the purpose of your life.
When you have finished with the worldly things, don't forget to remember yourself,
and to forget the world. Otherwise in the end your life is truly empty.

To make your life full, study the scriptures which teach the above truth of life.

Have faith and trust that their knowledge will give you eternal peace.

Swami Vishnu Ananda Saraswati

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